

Production System Vulnerability to Climate Change and its Impact on Poverty in Morocco: The Case of Saïss

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Abstract - Establishing a comprehensive baseline and information on the farming system and socioeconomic variables including population size and structure, livelihoods and income, household assets, physical, social, human and financial resources, land property rights, agricultural production systems, intensification, agro-biodiversity, rangeland utilization, animal husbandry and feeding calendar and sources, and technical status of crops is essential for developing appropriate rural development indicators. It will provide guidelines and target specific questions and problems for better understanding of rural communities' adaptation and production system vulnerability to climate change. The perception of poverty, production systems vulnerability and the household's behavior can enrich the reflection on the indicators for measuring poverty in rural areas and developing target strategies for sustainable agricultural development. In fact, the fundamental objectives of this work consist of the following questions: (i) what are the geographical characteristics of the production systems in the studied communities? (ii) which rural poor are vulnerable to climate change and who are among them are facing food insecurity? and, finally (iii) what are the differences between vulnerable households exposed to poverty and those who are not in the three sites of the Saïss-Meknes region? It's important to consider national context when conducting this analysis and also consider the national and regional trends with regard to poverty using available data and documentation. The production system characterization on the basis of structural and operational data can provide information on the behavior of farmers, the level of

efficiency and also help explaining socio-economic phenomena such as poverty and adaptation or not to climate change. The three communities studied showed differences in the diversity of production systems, the use of irrigation, the human capital, the financial and land capital. All these elements are the basis for differentiation of production systems, farmer's capacity for adaptation or resilience, exposure to poverty and food insecurity. Up to the survey, the most frequent climatic events in this region are drought, crop failure, storms, and floods. Farmers have therefore developed adaptation mechanisms to cope with the effects of these events. So, it was noted that the majority of respondents (55% to 70%) affirmed that they did nothing in the situation of climatic shocks encountered. The food security analysis showed a trend towards food insecurity in the three communities with a slight vulnerability in Sidi Slimane site. The estimation of food insecurity index confirmed this result. It's important to notice that agriculture is vulnerable to climate change, but this vulnerability depends on farm size and capital. However, households in the three localities are exposed to food insecurity and consequently to poverty. We cannot comment at this level of analysis on exposure to hunger, but we are more at a level of accessibility to food on a regular basis. Finally, if we consider income distribution and per capita, the level of poverty is relatively high.

Keywords: *Vulnerability, Agriculture, Food Security, Poverty, Saïss*

Changement climatique, vulnérabilité des systèmes de production agricoles et impact sur la pauvreté au Maroc : Cas du Saïss

Mots clés : Vulnérabilité, Agriculture, Sécurité Alimentaire, Pauvreté, Sais.

Résumé - La perception de la pauvreté à la vulnérabilité des systèmes de production et le comportement des agriculteurs est en mesure d'enrichir la réflexion sur les indicateurs de mesure de la pauvreté en milieu rural. En fait, les objectifs fondamentaux de ce travail consistent en les questions suivantes : (i) quelles sont les caractéristiques géographiques des systèmes de production dans chaque site étudié ? (ii) quels sont les pauvres ruraux vulnérables au changement climatique et qui sont confrontés à l'insécurité alimentaire ? et, enfin (iii) quelles sont les caractéristiques de distinction entre les ménages vulnérables et exposés à la pauvreté et ceux qui ne le sont pas dans les trois sites d'étude de la région de Saïss-Meknès ? Il est nécessaire de placer cette analyse dans son contexte national et aussi les tendances nationales et régionales en ce qui concerne la pauvreté compte tenu des documentations et données disponibles sur la région. La hiérarchisation des systèmes de production sur la base de données de structure et de fonctionnement pourra renseigner sur le comportement des agriculteurs, le niveau d'efficacité et aussi permettre d'expliquer des phénomènes socioéconomiques comme la pauvreté et l'adaptation ou non au changement climatique. Les trois communautés étudiées ont montré des différences quant à la diversité des systèmes de production, le recours à l'irrigation, le capital humain, le capital financier et le capital foncier. Tous ces éléments sont à la base de différenciation des systèmes de production, des capacités d'adaptation ou de résilience, d'exposition à la pauvreté et à l'insécurité alimentaire. A partir des résultats de l'enquête, les événements climatiques les plus fréquents dans cette région, sont la sécheresse, la perte de récolte, les tempêtes et les inondations. Ainsi, les agriculteurs ont développé des formes d'adaptation pour faire face aux effets de ces événements. Dans ce sens, il a été constaté que la majorité des enquêtés (55% à 70%) ont affirmé qu'ils n'ont rien fait devant les majeurs chocs climatiques rencontrés. L'analyse de la sécurité alimentaire a montré une tendance à une insécurité alimentaire des trois communes avec une légère vulnérabilité de la commune de Sidi Slimane. Il faut noter que ce constat se confirme par l'estimation des indicateurs d'insécurité alimentaire. Combinés au changement climatique et à la vulnérabilité de l'activité, les ménages de ces trois localités sont exposés à l'insécurité alimentaire et par conséquent à la pauvreté. On ne peut se prononcer à ce niveau d'analyse à une exposition à la famine mais on est plus à un niveau d'accessibilité aux aliments d'une manière régulière.

التغيرات المناخية، وهشاشة نظم الإنتاج الزراعي وتأثيرهما على الفقر بالمغرب: حالة منطقة سايس

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ملخص - ان تصور الفقر وهشاشة نظم الإنتاج وسلوك المزارعين قادر على إثراء التفكير في مؤشرات قياس الفقر في المناطق القروية. في الواقع، تتألف الأهداف الأساسية لهذا العمل من الأسئلة التالية: (1) ما هي الخصائص الجغرافية لأنظمة الإنتاج في كل موقع تمت دراسته؟ (2) من هم الفقراء المعرضون لتغير المناخ ومن يواجهون انعدام الأمن الغذائي؟ وأخيراً (3) ما هي الخصائص المميزة بين الفقراء والضعفاء والمعرضين لانعدام الأمن الغذائي وأولئك الذين ليسوا في مواقع الدراسة الثلاثة في منطقة سايس مكناس؟ ومن الضروري وضع هذا التحليل في سياقه الوطني وكذلك التوجهات الوطنية والإقليمية فيما يتعلق بمكافحة الفقر مع الأخذ في الاعتبار المعطيات والبيانات المتاحة عن المنطقة. إن تحديد أولويات أنظمة الإنتاج على أساس البيانات الهيكلية واليد العاملة يمكن أن يوفر معلومات عن سلوك المزارعين ومستوى الكفاءة ويساعد أيضاً في تفسير الظواهر الاجتماعية والاقتصادية مثل الفقر والتكيف أو عدمه مع تغير المناخ. أظهرت المجتمعات الثلاثة التي تمت دراستها اختلافات في تنوع أنظمة الإنتاج، واستخدام الري، ورأس المال البشري، ورأس المال المالي، ومساحة الضيعة. كل هذه العناصر هي الأساس للتمييز بين أنظمة الإنتاج، والقدرة على التكيف أو القدرة على الصمود، والتعرض للفقر وانعدام الأمن الغذائي. ومن نتائج المسح، فإن الظواهر المناخية الأكثر شيوعاً في هذه المنطقة هي الجفاف، واتلاف المحاصيل، والعواصف، والفيضانات. ولذلك طور المزارعون أشكالاً من التكيف للتعامل مع آثار هذه الأحداث. وبهذا المعنى، لوحظ أن غالبية المشاركين (55% إلى 70%) أكدوا أنهم لم يفعلوا شيئاً في مواجهة الصدمات المناخية الكبرى التي واجهوها. وأظهر التحليل ان الجماعات الثلاث معرضة للفقر وعلى الخصوص جماعة سيدي سليمان... وتجدر الإشارة إلى أن هذه الملاحظة تؤكدها تقديرات مؤشرات انعدام الأمن الغذائي. وإلى جانب تغير المناخ وضعف النشاط، تتعرض الأسر لانعدام الأمن الغذائي وبالتالي الفقر. لا يمكننا التعليق على هذا المستوى من التحليل على التعرض للمجاعة ولكن على مستوى إمكانية الوصول إلى الغذاء على أساس منتظم.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الهشاشة، الفلاحة، الفقر، النظم الزراعية، سايس

Introduction

Morocco is characterized by high population growth rates, large and rapidly increasing food deficits, highly variable income levels, and limited natural resources, particularly arable land, and water. Climatic features, especially low and variable rainfall, limit the options available to farmers. Economic growth, increasing urbanization and associated increasing consumer demand are forcing changes in production practices that threaten the natural resource base of the region. Exposure to a high degree of climate risk is a characteristic feature of rainfed agriculture in the semi-arid areas of Morocco. A growing body of evidence links unmitigated climatic variability to poor economic growth in Morocco and all developing countries. At a more local level, climate exerts a profound influence on the lives of poor rural populations who depend on agriculture for livelihood and sustenance, who are unprotected against climate-related diseases, who lack secure access to water and food, and who are more vulnerable to climate change. Several mechanisms by which climate change impacts rural households combined with other factors put rural populations in chronic poverty.

Climate change is expected to intensify many of the challenges facing rainfed agriculture in Morocco. Extreme land and biodiversity degradation and extreme poverty go hand in hand in rainfed agriculture, where a combination of unsustainable land management and fluctuating weather conditions increase the vulnerability of the communities and production systems to climate change. Climate change combined with agricultural policy strategies have contributed to the development of new farming strategies and increased demand for improved technologies and natural resources.

The increase in temperatures, the variation in precipitation, the frequency and intensity of extreme weather phenomena, accelerate the pressures already exerted on agricultural production in the world through the growing demand for food, the shortage of water, pollution, and land degradation. According to the IPCC “climate change will have a negative overall impact on the yield of the main cereal crops in Africa, with strong regional variability in this reduction in yield”. In addition, several studies have confirmed the existence of a link between human activities (GHG emissions), climate change and the effects on agricultural productivity. Thus, an increase in normal temperatures will cause a reduction in the yield of crops and especially those who are not protected

(under greenhouses), and a change in the periods or volume of precipitation will negatively influence the harvested quantities, particularly for rainfed crops. Likewise, in several countries, data recorded an advance in phenological stages and a reduction in the length of the vegetative period. Indeed, according to a study conducted by Lobell et al. (2011)¹ showed that “increasing temperatures and changes in rainfall observed between 1980 and 2008 have already had various perceptible effects on agriculture across the world.”

It is certain that agriculture and water are the main sectors exposed to climate change and for which Morocco has developed a number of strategies contributing to the adaptation of agriculture to climate change and water resources conservation (Laamari et al; 2022 and 2016). Different examples can be cited; the Green Morocco Plan (PMV) for agriculture, the National Plan for the Water Economy (PNEE) which provides within the PMV strategy subsidies for a reconversion to drip irrigation system. Also, it’s important to notice the energy strategy adopted by Morocco and which is based on the use of renewable energies, using solar panels. This has resulted in the encouragement of the use of solar energy for pumping irrigation water instead of diesel or gas (Telleria et al; 2020). Also, the Green Generation (GG) strategy which is a continuation of PMV but favoring more the social aspect.

Finally, it is important to note that at the farm level several adaptation mechanisms have been adopted by farmers such as diversification, alternative crops, livestock management, diversification of income-generating activities, production technologies and storage. Even the lifestyle of rural households was adapted to climate change (ACCA Project, 2007). Such adaptation of agricultural practices explains the vulnerability of production systems to climate change and, consequently, their economic performance. Therefore, it is certain that climate change induces considerable impacts on the cropping system, livestock, and income.

In this research we have tried to explain poverty by production system vulnerability to climate change and food insecurity. To do so, we have introduced new tools for analyzing vulnerability and food security. Thus, it will be possible to identify the main socio-economic factors who positively or negatively influence the behavior of a farmer to adopt adaptation mechanisms to climate change. Different approaches based on descriptives statistics, econometric models and trend analysis are used. The data used in this analysis of the production system vulnerability was collected

¹ Lobell, D.B., Schlenker, W. et Costa-Roberts, J. (2011). « Climate Trends and Global Crop Production Since 1980». VOL 333 SCIENCE www.sciencemag.org

as part of the CGIAR-CRP1² program carried out in the Saiss region, PhD research carried in collaboration with Hassan 1st University Settat, Faculty of Economics and INRA research studies. It should be noted that the results reported in this work concern three rural communities which are Ain Jamaa and Sidi Slimane Moul Kifane from the Province of Meknes and Bitit from the Province of Elhajeb.

Methodology and main production system characteristics

Methodology

The study conducted in two steps; the first one was based on rapid rural appraisal approach to identify the appropriate communities and, the second one was based on a field survey. The survey was conducted on a random sample of farmers stratified on three sites representing the different agrosystems of the Saiss region (map 1). The Meknes-Saiss action site covers an area of approximately 1694 km² in northern Morocco, and the total population of the site according to 2004 census was 714,000 people, with the percentage of the site's rural population being 20 %. This action site has a semi-arid to subhumid moisture regime, as determined by the balance between precipitation and

potential evapotranspiration. Average annual precipitation is relatively high, ranging from 500 to 800 mm on average. Most of the site reaches a level of 500 to 600 mm. Precipitation is higher on the hills, towards El Hajeb. Interannual precipitation variability is moderate, with a coefficient of variation of 24%. However, the risk of drought remains high, particularly at the beginning and middle of the growing season. The rains start in winter and distributed over the season, with on average of 90% of all precipitation concentrated between November and April. Most of the land on the site is allocated to agriculture. Natural forest lands are small and degraded. In general, all land is dominated by rainfed crops. Fruit trees are very important and are mainly concentrated along the eastern hills. In the northwest plain, rainfed and irrigated crops are dominant. Given this biodiversity, we notice three major differentiated agricultural ecosystems:

- The North-West plain with a mixture of rainfed and irrigated crops using groundwater source for irrigation.
- The hills dominated by fruit trees and olives to the East.
- Plains and low hills dominated by rainfed agriculture in most of the area.

Map 1. Location of the CRP1 site in Meknes-Fes and Morocco maps

The rainfed mixed production system is dominating in the tree sites. The crops in this system are primarily rainfed, also some communities are practicing supplementary irrigation on wheat and full irrigation for cash crops are developing rapidly. We find tree crops (olives and fruit trees) and grapes. Common crops are wheat, chickpeas, lentils, faba bean and fodder crops. Many farms are intensively capitalized with a

high level of inputs, and farmers are very sensitive to market opportunities. There are a number of specialized dairy and poultry systems within this ecological zone. These may also include summer crops grown following fallow or with some supplementary irrigation. Agriculture is facing many production constraints such as poor access to quality land, increasing numbers of small farmers, soil erosion on slopes

² *CRR11: CRP-Dryland system research program funded by CGIAR (2012-2015)*

during rainstorms, and erosion by wind, over-cultivated, exposed soils. However, the urban agglomeration of Meknes occupies a large part of agricultural area.

The research methodology adopted in the study aimed to consider geographical diversity and the representativeness of different ecosystems: plain and mountain, rainfed and irrigated, intensive and extensive agriculture. As the aim is to develop a database that inform on the vulnerability of production systems and rural households, it was necessary to capture this diversity in order to identify the different mechanisms of complementarity and strategies of farmers facing the risks, market dynamics and climate change. Considering the size of the questionnaire and the complexity of the questions and taking into consideration the budget and the time constraints allocated to the survey; a random sample

of 508 households (1.4% of the total population) was selected from the two provinces focusing on three locations. The sampling strategy was based on the spatial distribution of villages and the representativeness of households. Thus, different criteria were used such as the distance between municipalities and douars and also the size of the farm. Multistage random sampling technique was used. Villages were randomly selected using topographic maps of the selected sites. The random number table was used to draw the random sample of douars. A subgroup of 28 douars is selected randomly, which represents 49% of the total douars in the three localities. The distribution of the selected douars was as follows: 14 douars in Ain Jemaa out of a total of 29; 10 douars for Sidi Slimane out of a total of 20, and 4 douars for Bitit out of a total of 8. The final sample is as reported in table 1.

Table 1. Sample distribution among districts

	Location			Total
	Ain Jemaa	Sidi Slimane	Bitit	
Sample Size	229	137	142	508
Provinces	Meknes	Meknes	Hajeb	
No. of Selected Villages	14	10	4	28
Sex of the household head				
- Males	205	120	137	462
- Females	1	3	0	4
Holding Categories				
- ≤ 2 ha	15.4%	32.4%	54.6%	31.0%
- 2 – 5 ha	25.6%	38.2%	24.8%	28.8%
- 5 – 10 ha	26.9%	25.0%	13.5%	22.6%
- 10 – 20 ha	18.9%	4.4%	3.5%	10.7%
- > 20 ha	13.2%	32.4%	3.5%	6.9%
Average farm Size (ha)	13.6	3.9	6.2	8.9
Average family size	6	7	6	6

Schooling and level of education

It is important to emphasize that the level of illiteracy of heads of households is high in the three sites. According to the survey the level of illiterate heads of households is, respectively 55, 50 and 44% in Sidi Slimane, Bitit and Ain Jemaa. are illiterate (table 2). Regarding family members, there is a difference between areas and sexes. For males we

find, respectively 10%, 21% and 18% in Sidi Slimane, Bitit and Ain Jemaa. Regarding the female sex, we note an almost similarity in the results between the three sites. We have recorded 27%, in Sidi Slimane and 26% in Bitit and Ain Jemaa. These records are important to consider when establishing the poverty profile in the study site.

Table 2. Level of education of the household head

	Mal					Female				
	No level	elementary	Secondary	University	Coranic school	No level	Elementary	Secondary	University	Coranic school
Nbr. Sidi Slimane	79	194	147	12	3	219	92	65	4	4
% Total	10%	24%	18%	1%	0,40%	27%	11%	8%	0,50%	0,50%
Nbr. Bitit	181	153	100	19	10	230	105	71	13	3
% Total	21%	17%	11%	2%	1%	26%	12%	8%	2%	0,3%
Nbr. Ain Jamaa	226	214	199	35	12	323	152	88	12	0
% Total	18%	17%	16%	3%	1%	26%	12%	7%	1%	0%

Agricultural income and social equity

Farm agricultural income is one of the most used indicators in characterizing the profile of the poor in rural areas. Although it is an easily quantifiable indicator, even it is very complicated to identify all income sources nature. To better quantify the income of the surveyed households, it was necessary to identify the sources and their contribution to the overall household income. About five sources of income were identified including rainfed crops, irrigated crops, livestock income, extra-income, and other income sources.

At the regional level, it is clear that income is distributed in an asymmetrical manner with a strong concentration to the left of the curve (figure1).

Rainfed and irrigated crops are considered to be the main sources of income. Their contribution is about 67% of total agricultural income and livestock contributes about 18%. Other sources contribute about 15% and this contribution is far from being significant and generalized.

Figure 1. Income distribution

The average annual income at the three sites is 100,369 dh/household with a coefficient of variation of 260% indicating a wide dispersion of income. At the level of the three communities there is a respective annual income of 114,905 and 114,208 and 63,084 dh/household respectively in Ain Jamaa, Bitit and Sidi Slimane. The poverty profile of community members in the study area will be analyzed using agricultural income. We have limited this analysis to

household income because of missing data on certain sources of income.

Assuming the most used poverty line is US\$1.25 per person per day; It is estimated that nearly 27.4% of household members are below this threshold and this proportion is very high in Sidi Slimane compared to other sites (table 2). Thus, when examining monetary poverty in relation to land, we

find a high frequency of poor people in categories from 0 to 5 ha (71.6%).

To analyze the determinants of household income in the targeted areas, we studied the relationship between the annual income of the households and the farm size. The results of the survey indicate that the average annual household income is around 23,000 dh for small farmers compared to 450,000 dh for farmers who own more than 20 hectares.

Assuming the most used poverty line is US\$1.25 (11.25 dh) per person per day; It is estimated that nearly 27.4% of household members are below the poverty line and this

Tableau 3. Household monetary poverty distribution

	Bellow the poverty line	Above the poverty line
Sites		
AIN JEMAA	20.80%	79.20%
BETIT	26.20%	73.80%
SIDI SLIMAN	39.30%	60.70%
Farm categories		
Less 2 ha	39.50%	60.50%
2-5 ha	32.10%	67.90%
5-10 ha	18.10%	81.90%
10-20 ha	13.20%	86.80%
20 -50 ha	5.90%	94.10%
More 50 ha		100.00%
Sample	27.50%	72.50%

To better understand the distribution of income at the local and regional level, two indicators were used: the calculation of average income per person per year and the estimation of the Geni index (GI). Per capita income per day is calculated from data collected in the three communities targeted by this study applying the following formula:

$$\text{Income}_{dh/p/day} = \frac{\text{Annual household income}}{\text{Family size} / 365}$$

For the GI defined as being a synthetic indicator of inequalities of income distribution or wages and standard of living, it varies from 0 to 1. It is equal to 0 in a situation of perfect equality where all salaries, incomes and standard of living are equal. At the other extreme, it is equal to 1 in a situation of more possible inequalities of these parameters. It is calculated using the following formula:

proportion is very high in Sidi Slimane compared to other sites (table 2). Thus, when examining monetary poverty by farm category, we find a high frequency of poor people in categories from 0 to 5 ha (71.6%).

To identify poor households according to farm size in the targeted areas, we studied the relationship between the annual income of the households and the operated land by the farm. The result of the survey indicates that the average annual household income is around 23,000 dh for small farmers compared to around 450,000 dh for farmers who own more than 20 hectares.

$$GI = 2. [\text{Cov}(y_n ; F(y_n))]/\mu ;$$

With:

COV: Income covariance

y: Household income

F(y_n): Cumulative frequency of income

μ: Average income

The distribution of income per family member and per community throughout the year and according to Figure 2, 39% of the households declared that the members of their families receive less than 10 dh per person per day. More than 22% of these respondents stated that they receive between 10 and 20 dh per day as income per person living in the same household. In addition, only 28% of these households have between 20 and 60 dh/person as income per day. So around 80% of households in this region are poor. This observation is almost the same in all communities, in fact for Ain Jamaa about 26% of family members have less than 10 dh per person per day and about 52% having less than 20 dh per day per inhabitant. For Bitit community, 38% of its households declared that each member of their family receives less than 10 dh per day and around 58% of them receive less than 20 dh per day per person. This situation is serious at Sidi Slimane community. With 62% of households reporting that they have a per capita income per day of less than 10 dh, and 89% of them having less than 20 dh as an income per person per day.

If we consider the distribution of income per person per day to the land, Figure 3 shows that about 65% of small farmers who are operating less than 2 ha, receive less than 10 dh and 80% of them receive less 20 dh per person per day. However, 50% of large farmers who are operating more than 20 ha receive a per capita income per day that is greater than 100 dh. This is a classic pattern of small farm poverty. However, it is necessary to examine the distribution of this income in order to highlight the level of inequalities and try to link this inequality to current production systems, food security and vulnerability to climate change.

Figure 2: Household income distribution by community and farm category

Figure 3: Income distribution by farm size and per person and day

According to Figure 4, the distribution of income shows quite pronounced inequality among households in each community. In the Ain Jamaa community, the GI is 0.59 indicating a trend towards an unequal distribution of agricultural income between farmers. Compared to other sites and the region, this GI remains the least severe. At Bitit level, the GI is the highest with 0.73, indicating strong inequality in the distribution of income. With a GI of 0.61, the community of Sidi Slimane is also affected by inequality in the distribution of agricultural income. Basically, this is a

region where distribution is very unequal, reflecting inequality in using resources and improved technologies. It is certain that this inequality is explained by different factors, the main one of which is the importance of livestock and crops performances and the degree of integration into the market. The community of Sidi Slimane is characterized by the dominance of rainfed agriculture with production systems based on crop/livestock integration and a significant importance of the olive trees.

Figure 4. Lorenz curve and Gini Index by site and for the region

Therefore, it is necessary to link all socio-economic factors of the three communities to production system vulnerability to climate change and food insecurity. Based on that, the hypothesis of food insecurity exists and can be expressed differently when considering household behavior and climate and economic risks management.

Living standard as an indicator of vulnerability

To analyze the level of household vulnerability to food security and poverty, it is important to use the consumption unit (CU) per household. The concept of CU is used to take it into account when using the scale defined by the OECD. Once we have the composition and structure of the household, it is possible to quantify the CU by allocating 1 CU to an adult, 0.5 CU to children (14 years and over) and 0.3 for person under 14 years old. So, the level of living standard (LS) is calculated as follows:

$$LS_i = R_i / \sum_{j=0}^n CU_j$$

With:

LS_i = LS for household i

R_i = Total income for household i

CU_j = Consumption unit for member j of the household

Tables 4 and 5 indicate that at the LS at Ain Jamaa community is about 72.21%, higher than 60% considered as a low risk of non-coverage of consumption needs. However, when we examine the LS by household income, we find that household with 10 to 20 dh/day considered as have LS ranging 12 to 29%, very far from the threshold (60% line). The proportion of risk of non-coverage of consumption needs can reach 48% of the household members. Regarding Bitit community, the LS is high but associated with a high coefficient of variation indicating that the LS standard deviation is eight times higher than the average. But examining the median indicates a standard of living below the OECD standard. The respective poverty rate of 38 and 57% is observed at the level of income categories -10 and] 10, 20] dh/day/person. For the same income categories, the standard of living is far from reaching the OECD standard.

Tableau 4. Living standard distribution among communities

	Annual Income Dh	Total members of the household	Consumption Unit (CU)	Living Standard (LS)
Ain Jamaa				
Average	83,015	6.3	3.40	72.21
Standard Dev.	145,910	3.0	1.40	120.04
Max	134,000,0	26.0	10.70	827.16
Median	40,000	6.0	3.10	34.72
Bitit				
Average	98,359.69	6.08	3.09	242.00
Standard Dev.	368,005.95	3.31	1.57	1951,67
Max	4000,000.00	27.00	13.40	22,222.22
Median	30,000.00	5.50	2.80	28.94
Sidi Slimane				
Average	34,003.21	6.58	3.55	27.61
Standard Dev.	61,972.29	1.66	1.66	47.23
Max	545,000.00	27.19	12.00	369.24
Median	16,500.00	3.30	3.30	12.35

Despite the importance of irrigated agriculture in Bitit and Sidi Slimane, the poverty rates recorded for the different categories are higher than those of Ain Jamaa considered as a rainfed zone. In Sidi Slimane, the poverty rates are the highest. With respective rates of 62 and 86% for the income classes -10 and] 10, 20] dh/day/person, considered as a community where monetary poverty is almost generalized. Several factors can explain this situation. The structure and

distribution of land is a significant factor of discrimination. Even if the distribution of croplands is close to normal in this community, the amplitude is far from being close to that of the other two communities. In this case, it is important to consider property right and area distribution among these communities. So, we have different categories of poverty according to land wealth and property right security. Most of the farmers don't have a secure property right.

Tableau 5. Poverty and Living standard distribution by income per person and per day

Indicators	Income	Income	LS	LS	LS line
	-10dh/d/p	<=20dh/d/p	-10dh/d/p	<=20dh/d/p	<= 60%
Sidi Slimane	62%	86%	47%	72%	32%
Ain Jamaa	26%	52%	12%	29%	35%
Bitit	38%	57%	17%	38%	34%

Land tenure and property right security

In the Saiss demand for land for agriculture is becoming problematic regarding the intensification and the expansion of agriculture in the region. Strong urbanization and the development of agro-industry have had a serious impact on land availability and land's market. The urbanization and the use of irrigation have caused a strong demand for land. For the commune of Sidi Slimane, urbanization and foreigner investment in intensive agriculture have contributed to the

rise in land prices, and the development of new category of farmers who are considered as the main source of labor.

The distribution of land follows the distribution of income with the exception of the Sidi Slimane community. Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of crop land at the site level. It is clear that in Bitit farmers cultivate small areas because we are in the mountainous zone of Saiss. On the other hand, in Sidi Slimane, there is a tendency towards equitable distribution of agricultural land.

Figure 5. Land distribution among households

According to table 6, it appears that the private status (Melk) is dominating with a respective share of 78, 65 and 51% of the total area of Bitit, Ain Jamaa and Sidi Slimane. It's important to notice that land status Guich status is important

at Sidi Slimane community with 33% of the total operated area. In Bitit we also find the collective status and which, generally, concerns grazing area for small ruminant

Tableau 6. Land tenure

	Total land in ha	Private land in ha	State land in ha	Military Land in ha	Collective Land in ha	Rent land in ha
Sidi Slimane						
Sum (ha)	527,15	269,25	5,00	171,50	6,90	74,5
% of area	100	51	1	33	1	14
Bitit						
Sum (ha)	853,75	667,75	51,25	5,50	109,25	20,00
% of area	100	78	6	1	13	2
Ain Jamaa						
Sum (ha)	3105,45	2026,45	192,50	14,25	127,00	744,26
% of area	100	65	6	1	4	24

The state land is dominating since the region had thousands of colonization lands recovered after independence. These recovered lands were distributed to cooperatives as part of the agrarian reform (1969). These cooperatives themselves distributed the land among members, which triggered significant land transactions. In principle, this status is disappearing because of land titling and privatization. Based on the survey, the trend towards land security is greater in Bitit then in Ain Jamaa.

If we consider the land share of each member of the surveyed households, we find 0.56 ha/person in Sidi Slimane, 0.96 ha in Bitit and 2.12 ha in Ain Jamaa. It is certain that the water factor is important to consider in this distribution. But these figures already show that at Bitit and Sidi Slimane sites, where area per person is less than one hectare, land poverty must be considered. Considering the thresholds of 5 ha in irrigated system and 10 ha in rainfed system as a viability

line of a farm, the three sites can be considered as being below the threshold.

Climate shocks and adaptation mechanisms

Figure 6 demonstrates the percentage of surveyed households who faced climate shocks over the last 10 years and developed adaptation mechanisms. More than 51% of farmers declared that drought is the more frequent climate event, they have experienced this event 3 times during last ten years. With more than 25% of declarations, hail is considered the second important climate event in the region. Low yield and productivity due to the high temperature and wind at the end of the production cycle is considered as the third chock faced by 16% of farmers. during the last ten years they faced a specific shock. Loss of income, illness of family member due to extreme weather, crop failure, and drought were more frequencies encountered by households compared to other shocks.

To cope with climatic variability, households have developed appropriate adaptation strategies. Several studies have demonstrated that climate change events can be studied through the analysis of farmers' risk behavior. Economic theory offers a diversity of analytical approaches and tools. In the case of Morocco and for all risk behavior studies in rainfed and even irrigated areas, different attitudes have been identified which are not similar from region to another one.

For example, in arid regions, farmers have a high preference for risk (Moussaoui et al., 1994) while in irrigated areas, risk aversion behavior is the most dominant (Laamari A., 2015). In any case, the two extreme cases of risk aversion and preference exist and have contributed largely to develop appropriate research programs and also contributed to perform new agricultural insurance system.

Households in the sample was asked on the adaptation strategies that they used to reduce the negative effect of shocks; most of the household answered that they did nothing. Figure 7 summarized the reply of households on this

question for drought, hailstorm, crop failure, and changes in livestock. For drought, most of household did nothing (55%), 20% sold livestock, 5% shifted to non-farm employment and only 4% providing supplemental irrigation for their crops

Figure 7. Adaptation strategies used by household for most important shocks.

Adaptation strategies used by the households in the sample were vary according to farm size. Figure 7 illustrates the responds of households on adaptation strategies for the drought shocks by holding categories as an example. The analysis shows that there were difference strategies used for each holding categories where most small holders did nothing (65%) compared to large holders (37.5%). The

responds of small holder were sold livestock (12.7%), less food consumption (3.2%) and shifted to non-farm employment (9.5%); while large holders answered sold livestock (37.5%), sold part of the land (12.5%), borrowed money from relatives or others (12.5%). The differences between adaptation strategies used by households were statistically significant at $p > 0.01$.

- For smallholders, around 65% do nothing, 13% have sold animals, 9% looked for off-farm employment and 3% have reduced food consumption.
- While for large farmers, 37.5% did nothing, 37.5% sold animals, 12.5% sold part of the land, and 12.5% borrowed money from relatives or other people.

Figure 8. Adaptation strategies used by household for drought by holding categories.

Identification of the main climate change adaptation factors

This part of the study aims to verify the hypotheses that have already been considered in the previous section. It concerns the relationship that may exist between the choice of an adaptation strategy and household’s socio-economic factors (poverty, education, land fragmentation, experience, infrastructure, health) which can influence their choice. This analysis will be conducted using factorial correspondence analysis (CFA). CFA is a classification of a certain number of variables selected from the database of the system vulnerability survey in the three communities AIN JAMAA (229 cases), SIDISLIMANE (137 cases) and BETTIT (142 cases).

Presentation of variables

The literature review on adaptation mechanisms to climate change and its relationship to socio-economic factors that can influence farmer’s decisions behavior, the descriptive analysis of the most important variables collected in the 3 targeted areas and site characteristics have contributed to identify the main variables that affect adaptation. Thus, the level of education of the farmer, his experience in agriculture, the size of his farm and his agricultural income were selected as the main factors influencing farmer’s

decision to adopt an adaptation strategy facing climate change.

Among the household adaptation strategies faced with the effects of a drought, we can find off-farm activities, selling or renting part of land, reducing livestock size, irrigation, adopting and using new varieties, borrowing money, changing life standard, in-country immigration, and many other measures. However, some farmers may not adopt all presented options. Thus, the modalities of the variables to be studied are as follows:

- The dependent variable “adopt action to face climate change”: This variable is qualitative binomial. Indeed, the responses of the respondents relating to this question can be classified into two categories, the first includes farmers who declared that they have adopted at least one adaptation measure with regard to an extreme climate variability (drought or other). The second category contains other farmers who did nothing as reaction to climate variability.
 - **Category 1: N_AD_ST : « Did Nothing Fait »** : this variable represents farmers who didn’t adopt any climate adaptation mechanisms.
 - **Category2: AD_ST:** represents all farmers who have adopted one of the listed strategies among all listed

strategies. Variable 2 « farm size»; according to this variable three categories of farms were identified.

➤ The explanatory variables

1) *Area used*: Three categories were identified according to farm size: small, medium, and large. We have identified the following variables:

- Surf_Expl_5ha: represents small farmers operating less than 5 ha.
- Surf_Expl_Entre_5_20 ha: represents small farmers operating more than 5 ha and 20 ha.
- Surf_expl_Plus_20 ha: represents small farmers operating more than 20 ha.

2) *Illitracy*: Farmer’s education levels:

- Sans_Niv: Farmers with no education level.
- Niv_Prim: Farmers with primary school level.
- Niv_Sec: Farmers with secondary school level.
- Niv_Sup: Farmers with high education level.

3) *Experience in agriculture*

- Exp_Moins_5ans: Farmers with less than Five years’ experience in agriculture

- Exp_Entre_5_20 ans: Farmers with more than Five years’ experience in agriculture and 20 years
- Exp_Plus_20 ans: Farmers with more than 20 years’ experience in agriculture

4) *Monetary poverty (income per person per day)*

- Revenu_Moins_20 dh: Family member with less than 20 dh.
- Revenu_Entre_20_100 dh: Family member with more than 20 dh and less than 100 dh
- Revenu_Plus_100 dh : Family member with more than 100 dh.

Factorial classification (AFC)

We have applied a factorial classification for the qualitative variables collected for the three study areas. The AFC diagrams are reported in the following figures by site. Concerning the municipality of Ain Jammaa, the component diagram relating to the application of the AFC on the data collected and which relate to the variables of the hypotheses put forward above is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Diagram of components in Ain Jemmaa

According to this diagram, we notice that farmers with income less than 20 dh, are illiterate, and those who are operating less than 5 ha, do not adopt any climate change strategy. On the other hand, farmers whose per capita income per day is more than 20dh, and with a level of education (secondary or university) and operating more than 20 ha practice climate change adaptation strategies.

As in the case of the Ain Jammaa community, Figure 9 presents the component diagram of the AFC application to data collected in Sidi Slimane community. Thus, according to this diagram we observe that farmers whose income is less than 20 dh and low level of education (without Niv, niv-prim), and farmers’ experience less than 5 years and operating less than 5 ha, generally do not adopt any climate change strategy. On the other hand, farmers whose per capita income per day is more than 20 dh, with an education level (secondary or

university) and operating more than 20 ha and those with more than 20 years of experience in agriculture often practice climate change adaptation strategies.

In the case of Bitit AFC analysis confirms the trend already observed in the two other communities. Indeed, for this community the diagram of the components shows that poor households with an income less than 20 dh per day, small

farms who are operating less than 5 ha and those whose head of the household is illiterate, generally do not practice any climate change adaptation strategy. However, farmers whose per capita income per day is more than 20 dh, with a level of education (secondary or university), and farmers operating more than 20 ha practice climate change adaptation strategies (figure 11).

Figure 10. Diagram of components in Sidi Slimane

Figure 11. Diagram of components in Bitit

According to the outputs of AFC analysis of data collected in the three study areas Ain Jamaa, Sidi Slimane and Bitit, as presented in the above figures, we can confirm that poverty, illiteracy, farm size, and experience in agriculture are among factors that affect negatively farmers' strategies and adaptation mechanisms to climate change (drought, storms, floods). However, high education level, large size of cultivated area, high agricultural income, and experience can stimulate appropriate behavior among the farmer in facing climate change events such as the introduction of new technologies, adoption of drought-tolerant varieties, the use of supplementary irrigation, and other conservation technologies.

Modeling and logistic regression

Binary logit model

Logistic regression is a statistical analysis method to predict a binary outcome, such as yes or no, based on prior observations of a data set. A logistic regression model predicts a dependent data variable by analyzing the relationship between one or more existing independent variables (Wikipedia definition).

The statistical model known as logit model is, generally, used for classification and predictive analytics. Since the output is a probability, the dependent variable is bounded between 0 and 1. In logistic regression, the probability of success divided by the probability of failure. This is also commonly known as the log odds, or the natural logarithm of odds, and this logistic function is represented by the following formulas:

$$\text{Logit}(\pi) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-\pi))$$

$$\ln(\pi / (1 - \pi)) = \text{Beta}_0 + \text{Beta}_1 * X_1 + \dots + \text{Beta}_k * X_k$$

In this logistic regression equation, $\text{logit}(\pi)$ is the dependent or response variable and x is the independent variable. The beta parameter, or coefficient, in this model is commonly estimated via maximum likelihood estimation (MLE). This method tests different values of beta through multiple iterations to optimize for the best fit of log odds. All of these iterations produce the log likelihood function, and logistic regression seeks to maximize this function to find the best parameter estimate.

The binary logistic regression (BLR) is used in this study. In this approach, the response or dependent variable is dichotomous in nature—i.e. it has only two possible outcomes (e.g. 0 or 1). The BLR model can help to determine the strength of influence of education, experience (know-how), farm size and agricultural income per capita per day as independent variables may have on the adoption of climate

change strategies. Within logistic regression, this is the most commonly used approach, and more generally, it is one of the most common classifiers for binary classification.

After identifying the variables that affect farmers' behavior and reactions to climate change, we will try to use econometric model such as the binomial logistic regression to explain this behavior. The objective of the model is to verify the relationship between adaptation to climate change as a dependent variable on one side and the level of education, experience (know-how), farm size and agricultural income per capita per day as independent variables on the other side. Indeed, it involves estimating the probability that a farmer will adopt or not a climate change mechanism. We are referring to the determining socio-economic factors of adaptation or not to climate change. Since the dependent variable is dichotomous, we proceeded a binary probabilistic model (binary logit). According to the literature, the dichotomous model is based on the principle that the population studied is divided into two categories. The first category contains all farmers or households who adopted climate change adaptation strategies and the second category with farmers who didn't adopt any strategy. We consider a sample of n farmers ($i = 1, \dots, n$). For each farmer, we record whether the event has occurred or not:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{The event occurs} \\ 1 & \text{The event didn't occur} \end{cases}$$

So, it's possible to estimate probability of occurrence of the event as the expected variable Y as reported in the following formulas:

$$E[y_i] = (\text{Pr}(y_i = 1) \times 1) + (\text{Pr}(y_i = 0) \times 0) = \text{Pr}(y_i = 1) \quad (1)$$

The objective of the dichotomic model is to explain the occurrence of the event taking into account the characteristics of consideration observed X_i for farmer i . According to equation (1), if we would like to explain the values of Y considering X , we estimate the probability that $Y_i = 1$ or $Y_i = 0$ for X_i , using:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Pr}(Y_i = 1 / X_i) &= \text{Pr}(\beta X_i = \varepsilon_i \geq 0 / X_i) \\ &= \text{Pr}(\beta X_i \geq -\varepsilon_i / X_i) = F_{-\varepsilon}(\beta X) \end{aligned}$$

Since the the distribution of residues is not skewed, we can replace $F_{-\varepsilon}(\beta X)$ by $F_{\varepsilon}(\beta X)$.

The use of the logistic law associated to a distribution function Λ , will allow as having the equation:

$$F(X_i \beta) = \Lambda(X_i \beta) = \frac{e^{X_i \beta}}{1 + e^{X_i \beta}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-X_i \beta}}$$

Hence, the logistic model (Logit) which the objective is to explain the variable Y_i as a function dependent variables X_i can be written as follow:

$$P(Y_i = 1) = \frac{e^{X_i\beta}}{1 + e^{X_i\beta}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-X_i\beta}}$$

The estimation of the logit model logit can be done through estimation of β parameters. According to the logit model, the estimated values of β will be interpreted as follow:

- If $\beta_i > 0$, the variable X_i has a positive (β_i) effect on Y.
- Si $\beta_i < 0$, the variable X_i has a negative (β_i) effect on Y.

Logistic regression

Binary logistic regression consists of estimating a non-linear model whose dependent variable is dichotomous and whose independent variables can be continuous or discreet. It does not require the presence of a linear relationship between the variables since the dependent variable is dichotomous. The logistic regression model makes it possible by predicting the probability that Y_i has occurred or no through the optimization of the regression coefficients.

$$P(Y_i = 1) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-X_i\beta}} \text{ Ou } P(Y_i = 0) = \frac{1}{1+e^{X_i\beta}}$$

Hence, if the predicted value by the model is more than 0.5 the event will occur and if it's less than 0.5 the event will not occur. The binary logistic regression consists of estimating a non-linear model whose dependent variable is dichotomous and whose independent variables can be continuous or discreet. It does not require a linear relationship between the variables since the dependent variable is dichotomous.

Presentation of the model

The theoretical framework of the binary logit regression model presented above will help to develop our model and analyze interactions. Indeed, the model seeks to explain the behavior of farmers with regard to adaptation to climate change based on the main factors directly linked to their behavior. So, the model will help identify the sign of the effects of selected factors in particular illiteracy, experience in agriculture, and farm size on the farmer's choice to adopt or not to climate change strategies. The model can be presented as follow:

$$AD_ST = f(Niv_Ins, Revenu_h_j, Surf_Exp, Experience)$$

The probability of occurrence of this event can be presented as:

$$P(AD_{ST}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\alpha_0 + \alpha_{11} Sans_Niv + \alpha_{12} Niv_Prim + \alpha_{13} Niv_Sec + \alpha_{14} Niv_Sup + \alpha_2 Exp + \alpha_3 Surf_Exp + \alpha_4 Pauvreté)}}$$

With:

AD_ST: Dependent variable, qualitative and nominal. It represents climate change mechanisms adopted by the farmers.

Niv_Educ: It's a qualitative variable indicating the level of education of the farmer with 5 modalities (Sans_niv : Sans Niveau d'éducation, Niv_Prim : Niveau Primaire, Niv_Sec : Niveau Secondaire, Niv_Sup : Niveau Supérieur, Niv_cor : Niveau coranique)

EXP : Quantitative variable indicating the experience of farmer in agriculture expressed in the number of years.

Surface_Exp : Quantitative variable measuring the farm size in hectares.

Pauvreté: A discreet variable referring to the poverty index (Poverty=1 the income in dh/day/person is more than 20 dh otherwise 0).

Constant: all the other factors not considered in this analysis.

Results of the logistic models

Bitit community

Tableau 7: Summary of the models

Step	-2log-likelihood	R ² de Cox & Snell	R ² de Nagelkerke
1	157,135 ^a	,237	,316
a. The estimation was interrupted at iteration 6 because the estimations of parameters have changed by less than ,001.			

According to table 7, R² Nagelkerke is equal to 0,316. This result confirms that the model is adjusted to the field data about 31,6%. To estimate the variability explained by the model, we estimate the value of Pseudo-R².

$$R^2_{logit} = \frac{-2LL_{original} - (-2LL_{modèle})}{-2LL_{original}}$$

$$0,20 = \frac{195,471-157,135}{195,471}$$

The final model predicts 20% of the variance of the probability that a farmer adopts a climate change adaptation strategy. Thus, we can calculate the difference between the initial probability (-2log-likelihood) which is equal to 195.471 and the probability (-2log-likelihood) after introducing the independent variables into the model

presented in table 7 and which is equal to 157.135, which gives the value 38.336. This value is evaluated in a χ^2 distribution, and its significance is presented in the following table on “model specification tests”:

Table 8. Model specification test

Etape 1	Khi-Chi-two	df	Signification
Etape	38,336	7	,000
Bloc	38,336	7	,000
Modèle	38,336	7	,000
Test de Hosmer-Lemeshow	14,639	8	,067

According to table 8, the Chi-square is significant at 1% probability level. These results affirm that the final model can be used to significantly predict the probability that a farmer will adopt a strategy of climate change adaptation.

The Hosmer-Lemeshow test indicates whether there is a significant difference between the predicted and observed values. We notice in table 9 that at stage 1 there is no significant difference at 5% level between the predicted and observed values. So, it's clear that the predicted and observed values are consistent.

Table 9. Variables of the regression model

Step 1 ^a	A	E.S.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
EXP_Ménage	,048	,015	10,565	1	,001	1,049
TOT_Sur_EXP	,111	,053	4,293	1	,038	1,117
Pauvreté	-,871	,397	4,804	1	,028	,419
N_Educ			13,124	4	,011	
N_Educ(1)	-,094	1,042	,008	1	,928	,910
N_Educ(2)	-,246	1,052	,055	1	,815	,782
N_Educ(3)	1,687	1,129	2,234	1	,135	5,402
N_Educ(4)	2,037	1,595	1,631	1	,202	7,668
Constante	-1,563	1,123	1,935	1	,164	,210

To study the significance of the estimated coefficients of the independent variables, we rely on the Wald statistic. Wald illustrates the difference in the model before and after adding the last variable. From this table we observe that the estimated coefficients of the independent variables are significant at 5%. Then we confirm that the variables “experience”, “farm size”, “poverty” and “Level of education” will help to better predict the probability that a farmer adopts a climate change adaptation strategy than a model that does not include them. Sign of estimated coefficients α_i indicates the direction of the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. This relationship is positive for the variable “experience”, “farm size”, “Level of secondary education” and the “Level of university education”. However, “poverty”, “primary education level”, and “no education level” variables are negatively affecting this decision.

Ain Jmaa Community

Following the approach used in the case of Bitit, the regression logistic model for Ain Jmaa has generated the results reported in table 10.

Table 10. Ain Jmaa models summary

Step	-2log-likelihood	R ² de Cox & Snell	R ² de Nagelkerke
1	272,442 ^a	,143	,190

a. The estimation was interrupted at iteration 4 because the estimations of parameters have changed by less than ,001.

Table 10 shows that R² Nagelkerke is equal to 0,190. This result confirms the model is adjusted up to 19% to collected data.

To estimate the explained level of variability by the model we estimate Pseudo-R² value.

$$R^2_{\text{logit}} = \frac{-2LL_{\text{original}} - (-2LL_{\text{modèle}})}{-2LL_{\text{original}}}$$

$$0,12 = \frac{306,603 - 272,442}{306,603}$$

The final model predicts about 12% of the variance of the probability that a farmer adopts a climate change adaptation strategy. Thus, we can estimate the difference between the initial probability (-2log-likelihood) which is equal to 306.603 and the probability (-2log-likelihood) after introducing the independent variables into the model as

presented in table 11 with an amount of 272.442. This amount generates 34.161. This value is evaluated through χ^2 distribution and its significance is presented in the “model specification tests” table 11.

Table 11. Model specification test

Step 1	Khi-Chi-two	df	Signification
Qtep	34,162	7	,000
Bloc	34,162	7	,000
Model	34,162	7	,000
Hosmer-Lemeshow Test	22,070	8	,005

It's clear that the Khi-Chi-two is significant at level 1%. However, the model confirms that the model can significantly predict the probability that a farmer adopts a climate change strategy. The Hosmer-Lemeshow test indicates the existence of an important deviation between predicted and observed values. We observe that in table 10 at step 1 there is no significant difference at level 5% between observed and predicted variables. We can confirm that predicted and observed values are coherent.

Table 12. Variables of the model

Etape 1 ^a	A	E.S.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
ANNEE_EXPERIENCE	,024	,010	6,195	1	,013	1,024
TOT_SURF_expl	,024	,011	4,522	1	,033	1,024
Pauvereté	-,628	,309	4,142	1	,042	,533
N_Educ			15,517	4	,004	
N_Educ(1)	-,471	,805	,342	1	,559	,624
N_Educ(2)	-,203	,853	,057	1	,812	,816
N_Educ(3)	1,137	,875	1,688	1	,194	3,116
N_Educ(4)	,614	1,221	,253	1	,615	1,848
Constante	-,423	,880	,231	1	,631	,655

Table 12 showed that the estimated coefficients of the independent variables are significant at 5% level. Then we can affirm that the variable “experience”, “farm size”, “poverty” and “Level of education” will contribute to a better prediction of the probability that a farmer adopt a climate change adaptation strategy than models not including them. The sign of the estimated coefficients α_i indicates the nature of the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. We notice that the relationship is positive for the following variables “experience”, “farm size”, “Level of secondary education” and the “Level of higher education”. On the other hand, “poverty”, “Primary school education level”, and the “No education level” variables are negatively affecting the adaptation strategy.

Commune Sidi Slimane

The same analysis conducted Sidi Slimane community and results reported in tables 13. According to this tables R-tow Nagelkerke is equal to 0.349. This result confirms that the model is adjusted about 35% to data collected. To estimate the explained variability by the model we estimate the value of Pseudo-R2.

$$R^2_{\text{logit}} = \frac{-2LL_{\text{original}} - (-2LL_{\text{modèle}})}{-2LL_{\text{original}}}$$

$$0,22 = \frac{184,309 - 143,937}{184,309}$$

Table 13. Summary of the models

Step	-2log-likelihood	R ² - Cox & Snell	R-two of Nagelkerke
1	143.937 ^a	0.262	0.349

a. a. The estimation was interrupted at iteration 5 because the estimations of parameters have changed by less than 0.001

The final model predicts about 22% of the variance of the probability that a farmer adopts a climate change adaptation strategy. Thus, we can estimate the difference between the initial probability (-2log-likelihood) which is equal to 184.309 and the probability (-2log-likelihood) after introducing the independent variables into the model as presented in the table and zqual to 143.937, that gives 40.372. This value is evaluated using χ^2 distribution and its significance level presented in the following table 14 “model specification tests”:

Table 14. Model signification tests

Step 1	Khi-Chi-deux	df	Signification
Step	40.372	7	,000
Bloc	40.372	7	,000
Model	40.372	7	,000
Hosmer-Lemeshow test	9.589	8	0,295

According to this table, we notice that the Chi-Chi-square is significant at 1% level. Then we can confirm that the final

model can be used to predict significantly the probability that a farmer will adopt a climate change adaptation strategy than any model who didn't include these variables (constant).

The Hosmer-Lemeshow test indicates if there is a significant difference between the predicted and observed values. We observe in table 14 that there is not a significant difference at 5% between the predicted and observed values. Then these variables would probably contribute to improving the model. The Wald statistic illustrates the difference in the model before and after adding the last variable. According to table 14, the estimated coefficients of the independent variables are significant at level 5%. So, we can confirm that the

variable “experience”, “farm size”, “poverty” and the “Level of education” will help to better predict the probability that a farmer will adopt a climate change adaptation strategy than a model who didn't include them.

The sign of the estimated coefficients α_i indicates the nature of the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. We notice that the relationship is positive for the following variables “experience”, “farm size”, “Level of secondary education” and the “Level of higher education”. However, variables such, “poverty”, “Primary school education level”, and the “No education level” are negatively affecting the adaptation strategy.

Table 15. Variables of the model

Step 1 ^a	A	E.S.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
ANNEE_EXPERIENCE	-1.765	.760	5.387	1	.020	.171
TOT_SURF_expl	.212	.081	6.854	1	.009	1.236
Pauvereté	.032	.012	7.430	1	.006	1.033
N_Educ			9.470	4	.050	
N_Educ(1)	-.738	1.534	.231	1	.630	.478
N_Educ(2)	-.528	1.537	.118	1	.731	.590
N_Educ(3)	.536	1.535	.122	1	.727	1.710
N_Educ(4)	1.358	1.737	.611	1	.434	3.890
Constante	-.205	1.761	.014	1	.907	.815

Food Security Indicators (FSI)

Food Consumption Score (FCS)

The average score of FCS was estimated using data collected on the three communities. The results reported in tables 16, 17 and 18 show respective FCS of 40, 39 and 35.5

respectively for Bitit, Ain Jamaa and Sidi Slimane. The estimated average FCS is in the range of] 28.5 and 42], which means all communities are facing inadequate nutrition and consequently a limited poverty.

Table 16: Food consumption score (FCS) at Ain Jamaa

Diet	Consumption frequency for 7 days	Power	Score FCS
Cereals	7	2	14
Vegetables	1	1	1
Fruits	2	1	2
Meat /chicken/fish	1	4	4
Milk and by products	3	4	12
Olive oil and fats	5	0,5	2.5
Sugare	7	0,5	3.5
Total FCS			39

Table 17. Food consumption score (FCS) at Bitit

Diet	Consumption frequency for 7 days	Power	Score FCS
Diet	7	2	14
Cereals	3	1	3
Vegetables	1	1	1
Fruits	2	4	8
Meat /chicken/fish	2	4	8
Milk and by products	5	0,5	2.5
Olive oil and fats	7	0,5	3.5
Sugare	7	0,5	3,5
Total FCS			40

Table 18. Food consumption score (FCS) at Sidi Slimane

Diet	Consumption frequency for 7 days	Power	Score FCS
Cereals	6	2	12
Vegetables	1	1	1
Fruits	1	1	1
Meat /chicken/fish	1	4	4
Milk and by products	3	4	12
Olive oil and fats	4	0,5	2
Sugar	7	0,5	3,5
Total FCS			35.5

Households' experience with food insecurity

The nature of data used for this analysis did not cover the eight experiences for the measurement of the food insecurity experience scale (FIES) and its relationship with the United Nations sustainable development objective 2 (SDO2) which aims access to food for everyone. The six types of experience with food insecurity are classified in order of severity of food insecurity. In tables 18, 19 and 20 they are classified by severity. According to the survey and considering the frequencies of occurrence of food insecurity events (weak,

moderate, frequent) it was possible to conduct a qualitative assessments of food insecurity. In the case of Ain Jamaa, the food insecurity gradient varies from low to moderate (Table 19). In the case of Bitit, the food insecurity gradient is weak. In Sidi Slimane, the situation is a little bit confused, the gradient is varying from moderate situation to sever insecurity. These results confirm the general trend of poverty in the three communities. Except in Sidi Slimane community where households are more exposed to sever food insecurity more than the others.

Table19. Access to food in Ain Jamaa

Food insecurity experiences	Frequency (%)	Importance		
		-	+/-	+
Did you worry that your household would not have enough food to eat over the month?	42			X
Were you or any household member not able to eat the kinds of foods you preferred because of lack of income to buy or inability to produce?	25			
Did you or any other household member eat smaller meals in a day because of a lack of access to food (either because of a lack of income or lack of household production)?	13		X	
Did you or any other household member eat fewer meals in a day because there was not enough food?	8		X	
Did you or any household member go to sleep at night hungry because there was not enough food?	8	x		
Did you or any of your members go a WHOLE DAY without eating because there was not enough food?	4	x		

Table 20. Access to food in Bitit

Food insecurity experiences	Frequency (%)	Importance		
		-	+/-	+
Did you worry that your household would not have enough food to eat over the month?	28			
Were you or any household member not able to eat the kinds of foods you preferred because of lack of income to buy or inability to produce?	20			
Did you or any other household member eat smaller meals in a day because of a lack of access to food (either because of a lack of income or lack of household production)?	10			
Did you or any other household member eat fewer meals in a day because there was not enough food?	7			
Did you or any household member go to sleep at night hungry because there was not enough food?	6	x		
Did you or any of your members go a WHOLE DAY without eating because there was not enough food?	-	x		

Tableau 21. Access to food in Sidi Slimane

Food insecurity experiences	Frequency (%)	Importance		
		-	+/-	+
Did you worry that your household would not have enough food to eat over the month?	40			
Were you or any household member not able to eat the kinds of foods you preferred because of lack of income to buy or inability to produce?	24			
Did you or any other household member eat smaller meals in a day because of a lack of access to food (either because of a lack of income or lack of household production)?	90			
Did you or any other household member eat fewer meals in a day because there was not enough food?	2			
Did you or any household member go to sleep at night hungry because there was not enough food?	2	x		
Did you or any of your members go a WHOLE DAY without eating because there was not enough food?	-	x		

Household coping strategy related to food insecurity (CSI)
 Through the analysis of household behavior to food security, it was possible to collect household's members opinions on

the different strategies for coping with food insecurity. Nearly 17 criteria have been identified and for which the frequencies are presented in tables 22, 23 and 24.

Table 22. Household coping strategy related to food insecurity in Ain Jamaa

Household strategies	Yes in %	No in %	No answer in%
Purchased food on credit	28	67	5
Borrowed food, helped by relatives or the community	8	82	10
Adults ate less food so that children could eat more	5	85	10
Consumed seed stock held for next season	24	67	9
Sent children to live with relatives	2	88	10
Bartered food or non- food items to buy more staple food	1	90	9
Used up savings in order to purchase food	13	78	9
Reduced expenditure on health and education in order to purchase food	4	86	10
Borrowed money from relatives / neighbors in order to purchase food	18	73	9
Sold HH poultry – chicken, ducks, etc. in order to purchase other types of food	11	80	9
Sold HH articles (utensils, blankets, building materials, jewelry) in order to purchase food	5	86	9
Sold small ruminant (animals) goats, sheep in order to purchase other types of food	17	71	12
Sold big animals (Cattle, donkeys, camels,) in order to purchase other types of food	20	70	10
Sold agricultural tools, seeds. in order to purchase food	6	85	9
Stopped smoking Cigarettes in order to save costs that allowed you to purchase food	7	83	10
Accepted food aid from an international organization or government agency	8	81	11
Purchase national bread wheat flour	3	87	10

It is possible to estimate the CSI through its households' members opinions, but it was not possible to capture the quantities as an indicator of food satisfaction. Overall, opinions on CSI reported in tables 22, 23 and 24 show a diversity of strategies differ from one community to another. In the case of Ain Jamaa, the use of purchasing foods on credit, the use of seed stocks, the sale of cattle and interactions with family and neighbors are the most dominant CSI. All these strategies can explain the

vulnerability of households to poverty, particularly credit and the use of the stock of seeds.

In principle, Bitit community has more diversified financial resources and irrigation potential. The most frequent household strategy to ensure food security is financial credit. This option is the characteristics of households with limited CSI options, and it make them households more vulnerable to food insecurity in the context of low production or drought. The same situation is observed in Sidi Slimane.

Table 23. Household coping strategy related to food insecurity in Bitit

Household strategies	Yes in %	No in %	No answer in%
Purchased food on credit	57	39	4
Borrowed food, helped by relatives or the community	14	79	7
Adults ate less food so that children could eat more	1	89	10
Consumed seed stock held for next season	6	86	8
Sent children to live with relatives	2	88	10
Bartered food or non- food items to buy more staple food	0	100	0
Used up savings in order to purchase food	1	88	11
Reduced expenditure on health and education in order to purchase food	1	88	11
Borrowed money from relatives / neighbors in order to purchase food	9	82	9
Sold HH poultry – chicken, ducks, etc. in order to purchase other types of food	4	87	9
Sold HH articles (utensils, blankets, building materials, jewelry) in order to purchase food	1	89	10
Sold small ruminant (animals) goats, sheep in order to purchase other types of food	6	85	9
Sold big animals (Cattle, donkeys, camels,) in order to purchase other types of food	13	78	9
Sold agricultural tools, seeds. in order to purchase food	1	89	10
Stopped smoking Cigarettes in order to save costs that allowed you to purchase food	2	88	10
Accepted food aid from an international organization or government agency	1	90	9
Purchase national bread wheat flour	13	81	6

Table 24. Household coping strategy related to food insecurity in Sidi Slimane

Household strategies	Yes in %	No in %	No answer in%
Purchased food on credit	<u>31</u>	69	0
Borrowed food, helped by relatives or the community	<u>10</u>	90	0
Adults ate less food so that children could eat more	6	94	0
Consumed seed stock held for next season	5	95	0
Sent children to live with relatives	0	100	0
Bartered food or non- food items to buy more staple food	0	100	0
Used up savings in order to purchase food	7	93	0
Reduced expenditure on health and education in order to purchase food	6	94	0
Borrowed money from relatives / neighbors in order to purchase food	9	91	0
Sold HH poultry – chicken, ducks, etc. in order to purchase other types of food	4	96	0
Sold HH articles (utensils, blankets, building materials, jewelry) in order to purchase food	1	99	0
Sold small ruminant (animals) goats, sheep in order to purchase other types of food	4	96	0
Sold big animals (Cattle, donkeys, camels,) in order to purchase other types of food	2	98	0
Sold agricultural tools, seeds. in order to purchase food	0	100	0
Stopped smoking Cigarettes in order to save costs that allowed you to purchase food	<u>10</u>	90	0
Accepted food aid from an international organization or government agency	0	100	0
Purchase national bread wheat flour	4	93	3

General Conclusion

The analysis of agricultural production systems in the Meknes-Tafilalt study region has shown that this area is characterized by a diversity of geographic landscapes (plains, mountains, foothills, etc.), agricultural production systems (rainfed and irrigated) and type of production (intensive and extensive). This diversity was identified through the socioeconomic and biophysics characteristics and the living conditions of farmers in this region. Indeed, the percentage of income variation is between 40 and 50%. Thus, almost of 80% of farmers are poor, more than 50% are illiterate and almost all of the infrastructure (agricultural, sanitary, education) are fragile. In addition, other factors such as the fragmentation of land, the lack of training, and the limited awareness of adaptation to climate change are determinant factors that can deteriorate living conditions and make production systems more vulnerable to climate change in the three communities. Opinions about the question on adaptation mechanisms to climate change showed that more than 50% didn't adopt any strategy as a reaction to drought, flood or and storm.

To identify the main socioeconomic determinants which influence the vulnerability of the production systems to climate change, in addition to descriptive analysis of the production system, a factorial analysis of the components (AFC) was conducted. The results of this analysis showed, for the three study sites, that farmers with low level of education, a daily income per person less than 20DH, and a limited farm size do not adopt practices and adaptation mechanisms to face climate change.

To complete this factorial analysis, and to consolidate these results an empirical modeling of the farmer's behavior to adopt or not a climate change strategy according to socioeconomic factors was applied. The outputs of the model showed that the level of education of the farmer, his experience in agriculture, his agricultural income and the farm size area playing a significant effect on farmers' decision in terms of choosing a strategy of adaptation to climate change. Indeed, a well-educated farmer has easy access to information on new technologies, he can seek information everywhere and even he can carry out tests,

experimentations, studies on a climate phenomenon in order to overcome their effects farmers' behavior vis-à-vis of climate change. In addition, a farmer with a large size can diversify the uses of land by selling, sharing out or renting part of it or he can invest more in equipment, irrigation technologies and contracting an insurance against climatic disasters. Also, farmer with more experience, high knowledge, good practices, and skills can gain more and be more efficient in using resources.

To complete this analysis, we have conducted other issues related to system vulnerability such as monetary poverty, food security and potential exposure to hunger. By extend this study, it was possible to link production system vulnerability to poverty and food insecurity using United Nations criteria. All studied communities are facing food insecurity and poverty with different accuracy. Thus, it is necessary to adapt intervention strategies of the government and public policies to alleviate the effects of climate change to the specific characteristics and adaptation mechanisms of rural households in Meknes region.

Finally, since poverty is positively linked to climate change, it is necessary to take into account the vulnerability of agriculture and the parameters that determine it. While taking these important results into account, we must also be concerned by human development through education, training, and awareness programs. It is important that target programs should consider the profile of poverty and also its interaction with other factors such as schooling, housing, agriculture, etc. It is important to note that this work has confirmed that the attenuation of poverty cannot be carried out without developing a resilient agriculture in Morocco by:

- Reducing economic pressure on agriculture. This sector alone cannot contribute to poverty reduction and other sectors should be concerned to.
- Saiss region has a geographical opportunity to be located in a region where the industry and agribusiness are developed. The region is well served by ENAM school for agriculture, the CRRA regional center of INRA and the AGROPOL.
- Legal status of land and land tenure are a constraint for investment and more efforts are needed to review the laws and credit procedures.
- Create new income generation opportunities for poor households. The INDH (National Human Development Initiative) has contribute to that since 2005, but additional efforts must be deployed considering the characteristics of households, the poverty line, vulnerability. In this perspective, it is important to

target specific training programs in relation to agriculture, agro-industry and other sectors.

- The region has ecological conditions and a history able to provide it with significant agricultural potential which can only be reached by adapted technologies to climate conditions, market, and local knowledge.

In addition, the designing and implementing decisions an adaptation strategy must be done through participatory approaches. In other words, the adaptation strategy should not be implemented in a linear or/and horizontal way but must be conducted in a participative and diversified manner according to ecosystems, time and the context of its implementation. This leads us to think of new development approaches based on the negotiation of integrated actions to consider considering the expertise of managers and local knowledge. Several studies have shown that farmers, for several years, have developed measures to adapt to climate change. Households have also been able to overcome periods of poverty in relation with climate change as in 40s, 70s and 80s. So, this experience must be highlighted through the implementation of mechanisms of alleviating poverty and improving adaptation to climate change. The new model of governance of development across INDH is still at the beginning (Ouard et al., 2011). Consequently, the INDH, the GG strategy and all the interventions provided by the public authorities can constitute a platform to ensure the governance of the economic, human, and social development of this region and can constitute to develop a model to be generalized in similar situations. Thus, good governance requires the implementation of this platform whose pillars are communication, commitment, and participation.

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